

**Effect of Acetone and Ethanol on Belousov—
Zhabotinskii Oscillating Reaction
using Gallic Acid**

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IN the present communication, the effect of addition of acetone and ethanol on Belousov—Zhabotinskii oscillating reaction (hereafter B—Z reaction) using gallic acid (H_2G)¹⁻³ as the organic substrate and ferroin as catalyst has been reported. The normal course of oscillation was affected considerably and induction period, oscillation period, total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation were appreciably changed. The results have been explained in the light of FKN mechanism⁴.

visually from the sharp colour changes from red to green. The appearance of a permanent green colour indicated the cessation of oscillation. The reaction was carried out in presence of acetone or ethanol as the case might be, in different concentrations as also in their absence. The results are stated in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The results indicated that the induction period (time of first appearance of green colour), total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation decreased with the increase of acetone or ethanol concentration. Visible oscillations also occurred even in the absence of ferroin. Thus no catalyst or indicator was needed. Under this condition, colour changed from brown to golden yellow (time of first appearance of golden yellow colour taken as induction period) and the oscillation period was higher

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF ACETONE ON B—Z REACTION WITH GALLIC ACID AS ORGANIC SUBSTRATE AT 40°

$[H_2G]=0.068 M$, $[KBrO_3]=0.20 M$, $[H_2SO_4]=0.88 M$, $[Ferroin]\approx 1\times 10^{-3} M$

Acetone % (v/v)	Induction period s	Periods of first 4 oscillations s	Average period of first 4 oscillations s	Total no. of oscillations	Total osci- lation time s
0	110	8, 10, 11, 12	10	—	Indefinite
5	68	6, 7, 9, 9	8	—	Indefinite
10	49	6, 8, 7, 8	7	40	339
20	38	5, 4, 4, 5	4.5	15	70

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ETHANOL ON B—Z REACTION WITH GALLIC ACID AS ORGANIC SUBSTRATE AT 30°

$[H_2G]=0.04 M$, $[KBrO_3]=0.1003 M$, $[H_2SO_4]=1.126 M$, $[Ferroin]\approx 0.5\times 10^{-3} M$

Ethanol % (v/v)	Induction period s	Period of first 4 oscillations s	Average period of first 4 oscillations s	Total no. of oscillations	Total osci- lation time s
0	108	10, 10, 11, 12	11	291	8538
0.14	114	7, 7, 8, 9	8	13	238
0.28	92	7, 6, 6, 7	6.5	8	81
0.42	84	7, 3, 4, 5	5	8	41
0.56	76	9, 3, 5, 5	5.5	5	29
0.7	73	9, 3, 3, 5	5	5	26
0.0*	111	30, 34, 37, 44	36	7**	987

* Without ferroin. ** After 7 oscillations detection not possible.

Experimental

Gallic acid, concentrated H_2SO_4 , acetone (ethanol in the other case) and a few drops of ferroin in H_2SO_4 were taken in a reactor. The reaction was triggered by adding a solution of potassium biomate. All the solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations as stated in Tables 1 and 2 were obtained for the media. Nothing was added during the run of the oscillation so as to obtain a closed system in the thermodynamic sense. The reaction mixture was stirred at a fixed rate. The oscillations were recorded

than that in presence of ferroin. After a few oscillations, however, these were not visually detectable. The oscillations at different acetone concentrations were more or less sustained indicating that acetone functioned as the substrate⁵ in this system. Further work for complete elucidation of the system is in progress.

References

1. J. S. BABU and K. SRINIVASULU, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1978, 259, 1191.
2. E. KORÖS and M. ORBAN, *Nature (London)*, 1978, 273, 971.
3. A. K. DUTT and R. S. BANERJEE, *Sci. Cult.*, 1985, 51, 408.

4. R. J. FIELD, E. KÖRÖS and R. M. NOYES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 8649.
 5. P. STROOT and D. JANJIC, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1975, 58, 116.

Kinetics of Oxidation of L-Cysteine by Quinquevalent Vanadium in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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SHRIVASTAVA and Dixit¹ reported the oxidation of L-cysteine by vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid medium and proposed a mechanism without considering the reactive species of V^V. According to them, the anion of cysteine takes part in the reaction mechanism which explains the inverse dependence of reaction on [H⁺]. No indication of the free radical formation was mentioned. In our earlier work^{2,3} on the oxidation of amino acids with V^V, we clearly observed the formation of free radicals in the course of oxidation; this, therefore, prompted us to reinvestigate the cited work.

Experimental

A stock solution of V^V was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (Reidel) in an appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid, and the solution was standardised by titrating against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator. Since the solubility of L-cysteine (NBC) in water is very low, its solution was made in sulphuric acid. The other chemicals employed in the studies were of AnalaR grade.

Kinetic studies were arranged by taking [Cysteine] and [H₂SO₄] ≫ [V^V], and the rate of the reaction was followed by titrating the unconsumed V^V in aliquot portions at different intervals with ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic results can be summarised as follows and the data are listed in Table 1.

In the presence of large excess of cysteine and sulphuric acid, the reaction shows first order dependence in V^V as is evident from the linearity of

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 30°

[V ^V] × 10 ³ M	[Cysteine] × 10 ² M	[H ⁺] × 10 M	μ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
3.88	2.50	5.0	0.502	20.16	—
2.50	2.50	5.0	0.502	19.05	—
1.66	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.79	7.50
1.25	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.53	—
1.00	2.50	5.0	0.502	18.91	—
1.66	5.00	5.0	0.502	40.94	8.18
1.66	3.88	5.0	0.502	26.79	8.04
1.66	2.00	5.0	0.502	15.48	7.74
1.66	1.60	5.0	0.502	12.52	7.81
1.66	2.50	5.0	1.502	28.10	5.62
1.66	2.50	7.5	1.502	40.40	5.88
1.66	2.50	10.0	1.502	52.53	5.25
1.66	2.50	12.5	1.502	65.12	5.20
1.66	2.50	15.0	1.502	81.73	5.44

Cysteine - 10 k₂, H⁺ - 10³ k₂

log (a - x) vs time plot as well as from the constancy of the first order rate constants at different initial concentrations of oxidant. The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both L-cysteine and H⁺ are found to be directly proportional to the concentration of cysteine and hydrogen ions, respectively, indicating first order dependence of the reaction on each. This is also evident from the fairly constant values of k₂ (k₁/[Cysteine] or k₁/[H⁺]) given in the last column of Table 1. The slope values of the plots of log k₁ vs log [Cysteine] (slope = 1.08) and log k₁ vs log [H⁺] (slope = 1.07) further support the first order dependence of rate on cysteine and hydrogen ion. A double reciprocal plot between k₁ and [Cysteine] with a positive intercept on Y-axis gives a kinetic evidence for the formation of complex between oxidant and cysteine.

Zucker-Hammett plot⁴, i.e. log k₁ vs H₀ and log k₁ vs log [Acid] are linear with slope value 0.66 and 0.93, respectively. A linear plot with slope value (ω) + 10.0 is obtained if drawn between log (k₁ + H₀) and log a_{H₂O}; ω value suggests the involvement of water molecule as proton abstracting agent⁵.

The effect of variation of ionic strength was studied with varying concentration of sodium sulphate at fixed concentration of the other reactants. The rate increases with increase in the ionic strength. For example, under the conditions [V^V] = 1.66 × 10⁻³ M, [cysteine] = 2.5 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ M and at 30°, the initial rate increases from 18.79 to 191.6 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹ when the [Na₂SO₄] was varied from 0 to 0.8 M. An increase in the percentage of acetic acid, i.e. decrease in dielectric constant of the medium enhances the rate of reaction. For example in 10% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid for [V^V] = 1.66 × 10⁻³ M, [cysteine] = 2.5 × 10⁻² M, [H⁺] = 5.0 M and at 30°, k₁ = 21.76 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹, while in 50% aqueous acetic acid, k₁ = 52.52 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹. A linear plot between log k₁ and 1/D with positive slope suggests the reaction to be of ion-dipole type. Addition of NaHSO₄ at constant [H⁺]